

FCT RESEARCH AND INNOVATION LANDSCAPE COUNTRY PROFILE: SPAIN

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About ENACT

ENACT is a knowledge network focused on the fight against crime and terrorism (FCT). The network is funded under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme in Cluster 3 – Civil Security for Society. The project addresses the call topic HORIZON-CL3-2022-SSRI-01-02 ‘Knowledge Networks for Security Research & Innovation’, aiming to collect, aggregate, process, disseminate and make the most of the existing knowledge in the FCT area.

The project aims to satisfy two major ambitions,

- Provide evidence-based support to the decision-makers in the EU research and innovation (R&I) ecosystem in the FCT domain, targeted explicitly at enabling more effective and efficient programming of EU-funded R&I for the fight against crime and terrorism.
- Act as a catalyst for the uptake of innovation by enhancing the visibility and reliability of innovative FCT security solutions.

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Overview

The Fight against Crime and Terrorism (FCT) domain is a critical pillar within the European Union's security research framework, designed to address the increasingly complex and transnational threats facing Europe today. FCT research aims to provide innovative solutions, tools, and knowledge to empower law enforcement, policymakers, and civil society to prevent, detect, and respond to criminal and terrorist activities across the continent. The European Union supports collaborative research and innovation through key programmes like Horizon Europe, focussing on multidisciplinary approaches that combine advanced technology with robust legal, ethical, and societal safeguards.

In line with ENACT's objectives, this flash report is part of a series of reports that reviews the FCT R&I ecosystem in each EU Member State based on their participation in EU-funded Security Research under the FCT area between 2021 and 2024. The data used for the report comes from the most recent data available from CORDIS and the Horizon Dashboard, combined with data processed by ENACT under its SKB.

Spain Infobox

Spain plays a relevant role in the FCT sphere, standing among the top recipients of EU research funding—ranking third overall in Horizon Europe, with an 11.7% return rate. Spanish entities are notable for their active participation in collaborative and cross-disciplinary projects, often assuming coordinator or work-package leadership roles. Spain’s research and innovation community is deeply involved in a wide spectrum of FCT-related topics, such as digital transformation, artificial intelligence, border management, cybersecurity, and the protection of public spaces. Its commitment extends beyond technological excellence to include significant contributions in regulatory development and the sharing of best practices for law enforcement and judicial cooperation.

The strong presence of Spain in EU security research reflects not only robust scientific and industrial capabilities but also a strategic vision aligned with both European priorities and national needs. This engagement enhances Spain’s reputation as a reliable security partner, reinforces its influence in European policymaking, and increases the real-world impact of FCT research outcomes both domestically and across the EU.

Country overview in FCT Research & Innovation

The country's profile in the FCT domain will be examined from three perspectives—policy coverage, functional coverage, and technology—in accordance with the EU civil security taxonomy (EUCST) [2].

FCT Policy Coverage

The policy coverage charts indicate Spain's comprehensive engagement in Fight against Crime and Terrorism (FCT) research and innovation policy areas. In alignment with the thematic areas defined by the European Commission under the FCT domain of the EUCST (EU Civil Security Taxonomy), Spain - due to its size and complexity - faces the entire spectrum of challenges, including organised crime, drug trafficking, human trafficking, terrorism, the protection of public spaces, and cybersecurity. The following graph illustrates the policy coverage of the participants, categorised into the main Security Research areas: OC (Organised Crime), TR (Terrorism and Radicalisation), CC (Cybercrime), and HSI (Other Horizontal Societal Issues).

Figure 2 - Policy coverage across Spanish participants in the ENACT stakeholders directory

This alignment helps explain Spain's sustained and notable participation, as well as its positive performance, in FCT calls. Spanish contributions are well distributed across major policy domains, such as counterterrorism, digital security, and border management, demonstrating strategic commitment and responsiveness to evolving threats.

The chart below shows that the highest coverage is around "Dark net (illegal markets / cryptocurrencies)," which stands out well above the other categories. This is followed by "Other forms of cybercrime" and "Economic crime, corruption and fraud," which also have notably high levels of participation. Significant values are also observed in issues such as "Protection of public spaces," "Other forms of terrorism and radicalisation," and "Digital forensics." In contrast, categories like "Counterfeit goods and documents," "Environmental crime," and "Community policing" display the lowest participation on the chart.

Figure 3 - Policy coverage at level 3 across Spanish stakeholders.

FCT Functions Coverage

Analysis of the function's coverage graphs demonstrates that Spanish entities are actively involved in a wide range of functions, from research and development to operational deployment. The data show a noticeable emphasis on functions that facilitate collaboration among law enforcement agencies, technology providers, and academia, helping to bridge the gap between innovative research and field implementation.

Following chart highlights that the most prominent function is "Investigation and forensics," which has the highest participation. This is closely followed by "Data, information & intelligence gathering management, and exploitation" and "Training and exercises." "Monitoring and surveillance of environments and activities" and "Detection of goods, substances, assets and people and incidents" also show significant values. On the other hand, "Positioning and localisation, tracking and tracing" and "Physical access control" present the lowest participation levels within the chart.

This broad functional engagement maximizes project impact, ensuring that research outputs are well connected to real-world applications in security and law enforcement operations.

Figure 4 - Functions coverage across Spanish stakeholders

FCT Technology Domain Coverage

Charts depicting technology coverage reveal the capacity of Spanish stakeholders to address a diverse set of technological domains within security and societal challenges. The country is particularly strong in digital technologies, data analytics, and artificial intelligence, reflecting a high degree of innovation and technical expertise. Spanish contributions also extend to interoperability solutions, cybersecurity frameworks, and advanced sensing technologies, reinforcing Spain’s role as a technology leader within Europe.

Figure 5 - Technology coverage across Spanish stakeholders

Overview of Spain's Horizon Europe participation metrics

The next graph compares Spain's and the EU's key performance indicators in the Horizon Europe FCT domain, highlighting Spain's strong engagement and specific contributions relative to the European reference figures.

Spain	34	2.56	€ 548,447.66	€ 510,161.26	14	€ 3,854,437.00
	Signed Grants	Average Participation	Average Total Cost	Average EU Contribution	SME Participation	SME Net EU Contribution
EU	41	18.12	€ 4,310,115.27	€ 3,987,660.71	172	€ 44,114,024.00
	Signed Grants	Average Participation	Average Total Cost	Average EU Contribution	SME Participation	SME Net EU Contribution

Figure 6 - Spanish project participation metrics compared to EU

In this period, 34 out of 41 signed FCT grants include Spanish beneficiaries representing a sizable portion of EU activity in this domain. On average, an FCT grant have 18.12 beneficiaries, out of which 2.56 are Spanish. Also on average, Spanish beneficiaries hold a 12.72% of the grants budget, showing a relevant involvement in project activities. With respect to SME participation, Spanish SMEs represent only 8% of the total number of SMEs involved in FCT grants under the Horizon Programme.

Overall, these indicators demonstrate that while Spain may focus on more specialised consortia and targeted projects, its participation remains robust, yielding meaningful returns from Horizon Europe security funding.

Based on the figures above and the table below, Spain ranks second, tied with Greece, in terms of signed FCT grants, and third in terms of EU contribution.

Country Code	Country	Signed Grants	Total Participations by Country	Net EU Contribution
EL	Greece	34	90	€ 26,290,653.24
ES	Spain	34	87	€ 17,409,733.00
IT	Italy	25	65	€ 17,590,799.90
UK	United Kingdom	30	52	€ 4,525,528.75
DE	Germany	27	48	€ 13,558,133.33
FR	France	21	43	€ 10,163,819.63
BE	Belgium	23	39	€ 9,606,930.16
FI	Finland	22	29	€ 5,954,334.86
PT	Portugal	21	28	€ 4,924,522.00
NL	Netherlands	19	27	€ 8,513,248.75
PL	Poland	16	26	€ 5,898,789.00
CY	Cyprus	18	23	€ 5,723,581.25
RO	Romania	14	22	€ 2,733,978.00
MD	Moldova	18	20	€ 1,288,120.00
AT	Austria	12	16	€ 4,347,636.75
BG	Bulgaria	6	13	€ 2,241,263.14
CZ	Czechia	10	13	€ 2,061,742.25
LU	Luxembourg	10	11	€ 4,401,443.75
CH	Switzerland	8	11	€ -
IE	Ireland	7	10	€ 3,456,761.80
SE	Sweden	10	10	€ 2,128,071.25
EE	Estonia	7	9	€ 1,177,348.75
SI	Slovenia	4	8	€ 1,201,050.00
IL	Israel	4	5	€ 1,761,025.00
RS	Serbia	4	5	€ 478,496.25
HU	Hungary	3	4	€ 1,731,153.75
HR	Croatia	2	3	€ 602,395.26
LT	Lithuania	2	3	€ 420,080.00
MT	Malta	3	3	€ 283,356.00
NO	Norway	3	3	€ 1,071,048.75
SK	Slovakia	1	3	€ 831,038.50
CA	Canada	2	2	€ 418,417.50
DK	Denmark	2	2	€ 107,375.00
XK	Kosovo *	2	2	€ 78,750.00
MK	North Macedonia	2	2	€ 67,226.25
TR	Türkiye	1	2	€ 160,432.50
AL	Albania	1	1	€ 48,750.00
BA	Bosnia and Herzegovina	1	1	€ 59,625.00
IS	Iceland	1	1	€ 42,430.00
UA	Ukraine	1	1	€ 135,000.00

Table 1 - Comparison of Spain to other participating countries in Horizon Europe for signed grants, total projet participations and net EU contribution

Participants Summary

Spanish participation in Horizon Europe CL3-FCT projects encompasses a broad range of organizations, including research centres, universities, industry, and public sector bodies. The involvement of both well-established institutions and emerging players signals a robust and healthy ecosystem.

Figure 7 - Organisational types of Spanish participation compared to the EU average in Horizon Europe projects.

Particularly significant is the active role played by Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs) and Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs), reflecting both scientific excellence and application-driven project designs.

When analysing individual participants by their type, the following overview highlights the current key organisations involved.

Top End Users

End User	Total Cost	Signed Grants	Total EU Contribution
Ayuntamiento de Valencia	€ 1,031,375.00	4	€ 1,031,375.00
Ministerio del Interior	€ 787,312.50	11	€ 982,312.50
Ayuntamiento de Murcia	€ 482,372.50	4	€ 482,372.50
Ayuntamiento de Madrid	€ 427,500.00	4	€ 427,500.00
European Union Satellite Centre	€ 390,632.50	2	€ 390,632.50
Departament d'Interior i Seguretat Publica - Generalitat de Catalunya	€ 191,408.75	2	€ 191,408.50
Gobierno Vasco - Departamento Seguridad	€ 186,687.50	2	€ 186,687.50
Ayuntamiento de Malaga	€ 133,125.00	1	€ 133,125.00
Ministerio de la Presidencia, Justicia y Relaciones con las Cortes	€ 130,575.00	1	€ 130,575.00
Grand Total	€ 3,760,988.75	31	€ 3,955,988.50

Top Research and Technology Organisations

Research and Technology Organisation	Total Cost	Signed Grants	Total EU Contribution
Fundacion Centro de Tecnologias de Interaccion Visual y Comunicaciones Vicomtech	€ 2,348,962.50	8	€ 2,348,962.50
Fundacion Centro Tecnoloxico de Telecomunicacions de Galicia	€ 997,662.50	2	€ 997,662.50
Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas	€ 381,250.00	1	€ 381,250.00
Cetaqua, Centro Tecnoloxico del Agua, Fundacion Privada	€ 217,812.50	1	€ 274,687.50
Eticas Research and Innovation	€ 200,250.00	1	€ 200,250.00
Fundacion Centro de Estudios Andaluces	€ 112,187.50	1	€ 112,187.50
Grand Total	€ 4,258,125.00	14	€ 4,315,000.00

Top Industry

Industrial Organisation	Total Cost	Signed Grants	Total EU Contribution
Etra Investigacion y Desarrollo SA	€ 1,368,437.50	2	€ 1,344,656.25
Atos IT Solutions and Services Iberia SL	€ 1,134,375.00	4	€ 961,537.50
Tree Technology SA	€ 958,875.00	2	€ 761,680.75
Logikers SL	€ 649,750.00	1	€ 454,825.00
GMV Aerospace and Defence SA	€ 355,750.00	1	€ 387,275.00
Atos Spain SA	€ 239,250.00	2	€ 0.00
Ingenieria de Sistemas para la Defensa de Espana SA -SME MP	€ 223,393.04	3	€ 0.00
Telefonica Innovacion Digital SL	€ 193,721.25	1	€ 233,843.75
Euro-Funding EU Projects Sociedad Limitada	€ 193,125.00	1	€ 193,125.00
Byron Labs SL	€ 189,750.00	1	€ 189,750.00
Etra Air SL	€ 186,875.00	1	€ 0.00
Zabala Innovation Consulting SA	€ 150,000.00	1	€ 0.00
Paradigma Innovation	€ 141,687.50	1	€ 99,181.25
Herta Security SL	€ 125,437.50	1	€ 125,437.50
Insikt Intelligence S.L.	€ 97,500.00	1	€ 0.00
Telefonica SA	€ 40,122.50	1	€ 0.00
Grand Total	€ 6,248,049.29	24	€ 4,751,312.00

Top Academia

Higher Education	Total Cost	Signed Grants	EU Contribution
Universidad Politecnica de Madrid	€ 761,250.00	3	€ 761,250.00
Universidad de Santiago de Compostela	€ 760,207.50	1	€ 760,207.50
Universitat Politecnica de Valencia	€ 657,500.00	2	€ 657,500.00
Universidade da Coruna	€ 361,112.50	1	€ 361,112.50
Fundacio Privada Universitat i Tecnologia	€ 292,500.00	1	€ 292,500.00
Universidad de Alicante	€ 232,500.00	1	€ 232,500.00
Universidad de Alcalá	€ 201,512.50	1	€ 201,512.50
Universidad de la Iglesia de Deusto Entidad Religiosa	155512.5	1	155512.5
Universidad de la Laguna	€ 149,500.00	1	€ 149,500.00
Grand Total	€ 3,571,595.00	12	€ 3,571,595.00

Horizon Europe FCT Proposals Summary

Spain demonstrates a high level of engagement in Horizon Europe calls, reflected by a steady and significant number of proposals submitted by Spanish entities. The data indicate a diversified participation across several topics within the programme, highlighting a strong alignment with national strategic priorities in research and innovation.

This graph presents a comparative overview of Spain's and the EU's performance in Horizon Europe FCT proposal activities, allowing for a direct analysis of Spain's contribution and competitiveness.

Spain	220	32	508	€ 114.227.286,00	15%
	Eligible Proposals	Retained Proposals	Eligible Applications	Eligible EU Contribution	Success Rate
EU	278	39	4458	€ 1.099.171.410,00	14%
	Eligible Proposals	Retained Proposals	Eligible Applications	Eligible EU Contribution	Success Rate

Figure 8 - Statistics for Horizon Europe proposal submission for Spain compared to the EU overall.

Considering the number of retained proposals with respect to the eligible proposals, Spain's success rate stands at 15%, slightly above the EU average of 14%. This underscores the quality and competitiveness of Spanish proposals in the highly selective European context. The data collectively indicate that Spain maintains strong participation, achieves competitive outcomes, and continues to attract substantial EU funding in security research under Horizon Europe, reinforcing its position as a leading player within the program.

Horizon Europe FCT Projects Summary

The number of projects with strong Spanish participation has increased, with Spain regularly occupying lead or key partner roles in many initiatives. Spanish organizations are well-represented in large-scale, multi-partner projects, often taking responsibility for coordination, work package leadership, or pilot activities.

Acronym	Project Title	Type	No.
EMERITUS	Environmental crimes' intelligence and investigation protocol based on multiple data sources	IA	7
PRESERVE	Protecting euRopean public spaces against Emergent hoStile drone thrEats thRough an adVanced multidimensional shield and cross-border intelligEnce	RIA	6
LAGO	LESSEN DATA ACCESS AND GOVERNANCE OBSTACLES	IA	5
ENSEMBLE	ENhanced AI-baSEd cybercriMe-oriented collaBorative investigation technologies and capabiLitiEs	RIA	4
PRESERVE	Ethical and Privacy-preserving Big Data platform for Supporting criminal investigations	IA	4
EITHOS	European Identity THeft Observatory System	RIA	4
NARCOSIS	Non-tARgeted foRensic multidisCiplinary platfORM for inveStigatlon of drug-related fatalities	IA	4
VANGUARD	adVANCED technoloGical solutions coupled with societal-oriented Understanding and AwaReness for Disrupting trafficking in human beings	IA	3
IMPROVE	Improving Access to Services for Victims of Domestic Violence by Accelerating Change in Frontline Responder Organisations	IA	3
POLIIICE	Powerful Lawful Interception, Investigation, and Intelligence	IA	3
RITHMS	Research, Intelligence and Technology for Heritage and Market Security	RIA	3
VIGILANT	Vital IntelliGence to Investigate ILlegAl DisiNformaTion	IA	3
ECLIPSE	PrEventing and Combating onLine and offline hate speech and dIsinformation through multidisciPlinary innovation, education, and awarenEsS in Europe	IA	3
DETECTOR	Deepfake Evidence and Technology for Forensic Content Oversight and Research	RIA	3
BTL-COP	Building Trust and Leadership to challenge glocal aporophobic crime in a police Community Of Practice (BTL-COP)	RIA	3
Ceasefire	Advanced versatile artificial intelligence technologies and interconnected cross-sectoral fully-operational national focal points for combating illicit firearms trafficking	IA	2
FERMI	Fake nEws Risk Mltigator	IA	2

Acronym	Project Title	Type	No.
FALCON	Fight Against Large-scale Corruption and Organised Crime Networks	IA	2
KOBAN	Identifying future capabilities for Community Policing	RIA	2
IAMI	Identity Attributes Matrix Initiative	RIA	2
SafeHorizon	Innovations in Detecting and Disrupting Crime-as-a-Service Operations	RIA	2
ISEDA	Innovative Solutions to Eliminate Domestic Abuse	IA	2
PERIVALLON	Protecting the EuRoPeAn territory from organised enVironmentAl crime through inteLLigent threat detectiON tools	IA	2
ForMAT	Forensic Methylation Analysis Toolsets (FORMAT)	RIA	2
2PS	2PS - Prevent & Protect Through Support	RIA	1
GANNDALF	A Ground-breAking collaboratiON framework realizing the next era of cybercrime Detection And muLti-stakeholder investigation For LEAs, judicial ecosystems, and citizens.	RIA	1
ARMADILLO	Accurate Reliable Portable and Rapid Methods And Technologies for Detectlon of GHB Substances and Prevention Against Different Forms of VioLence and AssauLt SuppOrted by These Drugs	IA	1
GEMS	Gaming Ecosystem as a Multilayered Security Threat	RIA	1
TENSOR	Reliable biomeTric tEchNologies to asSist Police authorities in cOmbating terrorism and oRganized crime	IA	1
TENACITY	Travelling Intelligence Against Crime and Terrorism	IA	1
OSPREY	Online Safety and Security for Protection of Public-Facing Professionals and Democratic Resilience	RIA	1
AMALTHEA	EnAbling a Model-driven deep understAnding of the roLe of gender Towards a Holistic solution against Extremism and radicalization Activities	RIA	1
SALUS	Strengthening law enforcement with advanced IoT forensic tools and enriched investigation schemes, realised by a Software Defined Network Security-as-a-Service architecture	ROA	1
SALVUS	SALVUS (Ensuring SAfer justice outcomes in onLine, including undercoVer, child sexUal abuse inveStigations)	RIA	1

This level of engagement demonstrates Spain's capacity to drive cross-border collaboration in R&D activities and make meaningful contributions to the overall objectives of Horizon Europe.

The following section presents a series of charts detailing the policy, functional, and technological coverage of the projects, based on the comprehensive list of projects outlined above.

Figure 9 - Policy Coverage according to projects with Spanish participation.

Figure 10 - Functions coverage according to projects with Spanish participation.

Figure 11 - Technology coverage according to projects with Spanish participation.

Final Remarks

Spain's role in European security research is marked by strong participation and leadership, as seen in the country's prominent position in Horizon Europe funding and coordination of collaborative projects.

Within the policy landscape, Spanish organisations are most active in tackling digital and economic crime, cybercrime, and counterterrorism, while also making important contributions in areas such as forensics, intelligence gathering, and operational training. This robust involvement is underpinned by a highly diverse research community—spanning law enforcement, academia, industry, and research centres—that ensures outcomes are both innovative and practical.

Regarding the functional dimension data show Spanish organisations are especially active in "Investigation and forensics," closely followed by "Data, information & intelligence gathering" and "Training and exercises." These functional areas reflect strong support for both research-driven innovation and operational capability-building, maximising the relevance of Spanish contributions to practical law enforcement applications.

In the technological arena, the data about Spanish participation demonstrates robust expertise in digital technologies, artificial intelligence, and cybersecurity. The country also advances interoperability and sensing solutions, evidencing a broad technological capacity that supports national and European priorities in the security sector.

Spanish organisations account for a substantial proportion of consortium partners and allocated funding in funded Horizon Europe security projects. Most consortia include Spanish partners, and the success rate of Spanish proposals exceeds the EU average, reinforcing Spain's reputation as a competitive, innovative, and reliable contributor.

Collectively, these strengths support a security innovation ecosystem that is mature, versatile, and fully aligned with evolving European and domestic challenges.

For more information and guidance regarding the Spanish participation in CL3 and possible collaboration opportunities, please visit the National Contact Points Portal: <https://horizoneuropencppportal.eu/> and search for the Spanish NCPs.

A note on data sources

The data used to compile this report is from the following sources

- ENACT stakeholder directory where relevant organisations participating in Horizon Europe, Horizon 2020 or relevant security events have been compiled and categorised according to the EU Civil Security Market Taxonomy for policy levels two and three, functions and technology.
- ENACT Project Directory where relevant projects have been compiled and categorised according to the EU Civil Security Market Taxonomy for policy levels two and three, functions and technology.
- The Horizon Dashboard for R&I Projects and R&I Proposals [1]

An explorable version of the ENACT Stakeholders Directory is available on the ENACT website [2].

[1] Horizon Dashboard - <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/horizon-dashboard>

[2] ENACT Stakeholders Map - <https://enact-eu.net/enact-fct-stakeholder-map/>

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